

The ontogeny of asymmetry in echolocating whales

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Abstract

Extreme asymmetry of the skull is one of the most distinctive traits that characterizes toothed whales (Odontoceti, Cetacea). The origin and function of cranial asymmetry are connected to the evolution of echolocation, the ability to use high frequency sounds to navigate the surrounding environment. Although this novel phenotype must arise through changes in cranial development, the ontogeny of cetacean asymmetry has never been investigated. Here we use three-dimensional geometric morphometrics to quantify the changes in degree of asymmetry and skull shape during prenatal and postnatal ontogeny for five genera spanning odontocete diversity (oceanic dolphins, porpoises, and beluga). Asymmetry in early ontogeny starts low and tracks phylogenetic relatedness of taxa. Distantly-related taxa that share aspects of their ecology overwrite these initial differences via heterochronic shifts, ultimately converging on comparable high levels of skull asymmetry. Porpoises maintain low levels of asymmetry into maturity and present a decelerated rate of growth, likely retained from the ancestral condition. Ancestral state reconstruction of allometric trajectories demonstrates that both paedomorphism and peramorphism contribute to cranial shape diversity across odontocetes. This study provides a striking example of how divergent developmental pathways can produce convergent ecological adaptations, even for some of the most unusual phenotypes exhibited among vertebrates.

Keywords: evolutionary developmental biology, geometric morphometrics, Cetacea, echolocation

1. Introduction

Skull asymmetry is a rare trait in tetrapods and is usually limited to specific areas of the skull related to sensory abilities, as in some owls displaying asymmetry between the ear canals to allow for directional hearing [1]. Toothed whales (Odontoceti, Cetacea) are one such group with marked directional cranial asymmetry [2], a trait which was acquired in parallel with their ability to echolocate [3]: using high-frequency sounds over 100 kHz to better navigate the complex water environment, locate prey, and communicate with co-specifics efficiently [4]. Among mammals, only some bats [5] and a few species of shrews [6] have also convergently evolved the ability to echolocate. This strong directional asymmetry heavily influenced skull evolution in odontocetes [2, 3, 7], including driving unique patterns of phenotypic integration among cranial bones [8].

The ancestors of modern whales, archaeocetes, may have possessed some level of cranial asymmetry in the rostral region to support directional hearing [2, 9]. The other living cetacean clade, baleen whales (Mysticeti), have symmetrical crania, similar to that of the closely related modern even-toed ungulates [10], and employ only low frequency sounds for communication [11]. In adult modern odontocetes, asymmetry is mostly prominent in the neurocranium and nasal openings [2, 12]. The bones of the right side of the skull are typically larger and expand leftward, reflecting the morphology of the overlying soft tissues [2, 13], in particular the melon, the fat body that is involved in focusing and transmitting high frequency sounds to the surrounding water, and the phonic lips, valves located in the nasals passages that control sound emission [11, 14]. It has been shown that varying levels of asymmetry in odontocetes are directly correlated with production of sound and its frequency [13, 15], as well as in directionality of hearing [9].

While evolutionary changes in skull asymmetry and its possible drivers have been studied extensively in Odontoceti [e.g. 2, 12, 13], the developmental origin of this trait remains largely unexplored, despite the established importance of ontogenetic shifts in the rise of other unique cetacean traits, such as hind limb reduction or tooth loss [16, 17]. Here, we address this gap with a quantitative analysis to answer the question: how does skull asymmetry develop in toothed whales?

We approach this question by applying landmark-based 3D geometric morphometrics (GM) methods in a dataset that represents all prenatal and postnatal growth stages of an ecologically and taxonomically diverse selection of modern odontocetes: Delphinidae (oceanic dolphins – *Stenella* and *Lagenorhynchus*, pilot whales – *Globicephala*), Monodontidae (beluga – *Delphinapterus*), and Phocoenidae (porpoises – *Phocoena*). With these data, we characterize both degree and pattern of asymmetry and skull shape through ontogeny to understand the role of ecological adaptations and phylogenetic relationships in determining the development and evolution of skull asymmetry.

2. Results

(a) The ontogeny of asymmetry

Cranial asymmetry was quantified through ontogeny as the overall mean Euclidean distance between directional asymmetric (DA) and symmetric shape, after excluding the variably present interparietal bone [18] (Materials and Methods). Asymmetry starts at relatively low levels in the early fetal stages of all taxa and is closely aligned with phylogenetic relationship, with *Delphinapterus* and *Phocoena* sharing a more symmetric cranial shape relative to the three species of Delphinidae (figure 1, electronic supplementary material, figure S1, table S1). Ontogenetic trajectories of asymmetry then diverge markedly. Asymmetry increases particularly rapidly between the early fetal stages and birth in *Delphinapterus*, while *Phocoena* maintains significantly lower levels for its entire growth, although in both taxa the only significant increase in asymmetry levels is in the prenatal growth phase and then they stabilize postnatally. This steep increase allows *Delphinapterus* to reach high levels of asymmetry comparable to *Globicephala* in the juvenile stage. The three sampled species of Delphinidae increase asymmetry more gradually, with significant changes only occurring in the postnatal stages in *Lagenorhynchus* and *Globicephala*. Among adult specimens,

92 the three delphinids (*Lagenorhynchus*, *Stenella*, *Globicephala*) and the monodontids
93 (*Delphinapterus*) displayed significantly higher levels of asymmetry than the phocoid (*Phocoena*).
94 *Globicephala* also presents a more asymmetric skull than the other oceanic dolphins
95 (*Lagenorhynchus*, *Stenella*). These asymmetry levels found in the adults are consistent with
96 previous studies [2, 13], and validate the methodology used here to quantify cranial asymmetry.
97

98 The distribution of asymmetry across the skull is highly divergent among taxa from the late fetal
99 stages (electronic supplementary material, figure S2). The low variation in *Phocoena* is distributed
100 throughout the cranium, and in closely related *Delphinapterus* is mostly concentrated in the
101 supraoccipital and nasal region, with a visible leftward shift of the skull midline (figure 1).
102 Delphinidae instead have high levels of variation in the neurocranium, from the antorbital notches to
103 the supraoccipital, with *Stenella* displaying a prominent asymmetry in the dorsal end of the
104 premaxilla. Therefore, while *Delphinapterus* and *Globicephala* present similar asymmetry levels in
105 the adults, the different distribution of the asymmetry still reflects their different evolutionary history,
106 as does their markedly different levels of asymmetry in early ontogeny.
107

108 (b) The ontogeny of skull shape

109 Phenotypic trajectory analysis [PTA, 19] of skull shape ontogeny reinforces the morphological
110 convergence between *Delphinapterus* and *Globicephala* and also highlights the peculiarity of skull
111 development in *Phocoena* (figure 2, electronic supplementary material, figure S3, table S2). The
112 phenotypic trajectories of all taxa are similar in shape but have unique directions. *Delphinapterus*
113 and *Globicephala*, the two most asymmetric genera, are characterized by a longer trajectory
114 compared to the rest of the dataset. However, the distribution of shape change in these two taxa is
115 very different, owing to their phylogenetic history. *Delphinapterus* has a very prominent shape
116 change early in the ontogeny followed by shorter shifts among postnatal stages, while *Globicephala*
117 has similar amounts of shape change across all growth stages. The other delphinids have distinctly
118 different trajectories that do not overlap with *Globicephala*, though they also display consistent shifts
119 in shape across developmental stages. *Phocoena* has a unique phenotypic trajectory, mostly
120 following a straight line along PC1 and with a very small shape change between juvenile and adult
121 stages. This is likely connected to its low and constant levels of skull asymmetry.
122

123 (c) Evolution of skull allometry

124 Another important aspect of ontogeny is allometry, or the rate of shape change relative to size [20].
125 When studying ontogenetic allometry, it is possible to not only characterize the trends observed in
126 modern taxa, but also to estimate the allometric trajectories in the ancestors [21] and in turn
127 determine the direction of heterochronic change between the ancestral nodes and the descendants
128 [20]. This allows direct testing of whether the patterns observed in ontogeny are due to the influence
129 of phylogeny or are instead brought about by ecological convergence. Since we found differences in
130 the prenatal and postnatal rate of change in both shape and asymmetry, we first tested if allometric
131 trends were also significantly different in these two phases of ontogeny, as has been proposed in
132 other mammals [22] and amniotes [23]. Our analysis identified a model with one varying break point
133 and with different slopes for each taxon as the preferred model (electronic supplementary material,
134 table S3). Within each genus, we found significant absolute distances in allometric slope and length
135 differences between prenatal and postnatal stages in all three Delphinidae (electronic
136 supplementary material, figure S4a, table S4). Allometric growth in Monodontidae and Phocoenidae
137 does not show a significant change before and after birth.
138

139 In comparing allometric slopes among genera, *Delphinapterus* and *Globicephala* are significantly
140 different to each other in all metrics during prenatal growth, but not postnatally (electronic
141 supplementary material, figure S4b, table S4). Additionally, both taxa differ significantly from
142 *Phocoena* and *Stenella* in prenatal ontogeny, while only *Globicephala* retains a significant difference
143 with *Stenella* postnatally. This result is consistent with previous observations that the level of
144 convergence between *Delphinapterus* and *Globicephala* increases progressively during growth.
145 *Phocoena*, while exhibiting low levels of asymmetry and shorter postnatal growth, does not exhibit a
146 unique allometric trend compared to the other taxa.

147 To assess which heterochronic processes generated these differences in allometry among the
148 sampled taxa, we estimated the ancestral slopes and intercepts for prenatal and postnatal growth in
149 the following ancestral nodes: 1) the common ancestor of Delphinoidea, the group that includes all
150 the families analysed, 2) the ancestor of Phocoenidae and Monodontidae, 3) the ancestor of
151 Delphinidae, and 4) the common ancestor of *Globicephala* and *Stenella*, within Delphinidae. The
152 regression plot including both modern and ancestral allometric regressions shows a strong
153 separation between *Globicephala* and *Delphinapterus* and all other taxa, both prenatally and
154 postnatally (figure 3a, electronic supplementary material, figure S5a-b). These taxa have
155 consistently lower rates of development. *Phocoena* instead presents a relatively conserved
156 allometric trend prenatally, which closely tracks its ancestral node, while postnatally it has a lower
157 rate. The only significant difference recovered between prenatal and postnatal allometry in ancestral
158 slopes is in node 2 (ancestor of Phocoenidae and Monodontidae). Evolutionary changes in
159 allometry are concentrated in prenatal growth, with most ancestral prenatal slopes are different from
160 each other and from modern taxa, with the notable exception of *Phocoena*. In postnatal ontogeny, in
161 contrast, only *Stenella* differs significantly from the ancestral nodes (electronic supplementary
162 material, figure S6a-b, table S5).

163
164 Combined, these observations allow us to characterize the direction of heterochronic changes that
165 have occurred during the evolution of these taxa (figure 3b). Paedomorphism, which is defined as
166 the retention of juvenile ancestral traits in the adult of the descendant [20], is recognizable by a
167 decrease in slope (deceleration) or intercept (post-displacement) in an extant taxon relative to its
168 ancestor. This type of heterochrony is recognizable in the evolution of Phocoenidae and
169 Monodontidae, in both prenatal and postnatal ontogeny. This process is particularly visible in
170 *Delphinapterus*, while *Phocoena* only presents deceleration in postnatal growth. Convergently,
171 *Globicephala* also shows decelerated growth relative to its ancestor both prenatally and postnatally.
172 In fact, the opposite heterochronic transformation, peramorphism, defined as the presence of adult
173 ancestral traits in the juvenile of the descendant [20], is present in Delphinidae. An increase in
174 intercept value (pre-displacement) is visible prenatally in the ancestor of Delphinidae and in the
175 other two oceanic dolphins, *Stenella* and *Lagenorhynchus*. Postnatal ontogeny of these same taxa
176 and nodes is instead characterized by higher slope values (acceleration). This estimate suggests
177 that the evolution of convergent skull morphologies in *Delphinapterus* and *Globicephala* occurred
178 independently via parallel changes in different aspects of development: an increase in asymmetry
179 levels in the first taxon and a paedomorphic shift in shape development in the second. These
180 changes were likely driven by similar ecological pressures. The unique phenotypic trajectory and
181 ontogeny of asymmetry of *Phocoena* instead are likely derived from its ancestral condition.

182

183 3. Discussion

184

185 (a) Shared ecology drives convergence in skull ontogeny

186 Closely related species display similar levels of asymmetry early in ontogeny, but asymmetry in
187 adults shows clear association with ecology, regardless of phylogeny. This convergence is achieved
188 through divergent ontogenetic trajectories in cranial asymmetry, which is most evident in comparing
189 *Delphinapterus* with the closely related *Phocoena* and the distantly related, but ecologically similar,
190 *Globicephala*. Both *Delphinapterus* and *Phocoena* start off with low levels of asymmetry but, while
191 *Phocoena* remains at a similar level throughout ontogeny, *Delphinapterus* has a steep increase in
192 asymmetry prenatally to reach similar levels to *Globicephala* (figure 1). *Delphinapterus* and
193 *Globicephala* also share other aspects of their skull ontogeny: they present similar phenotypic
194 trajectories (figure 2) and convergently acquired paedomorphic allometric growth (figure 3).

195

196 The clades including *Delphinapterus* and *Globicephala* diverged approximately 20 million years ago
197 (Mya) [24] and have since convergently evolved similar ecological adaptations, some of which are
198 reflected in their skull morphology. They occupy non-overlapping environments and geographical
199 ranges, with *Globicephala* found worldwide in tropical and temperate waters [25], while
200 *Delphinapterus* only lives around the ice pack in the North Pole [26]. Nonetheless, they share
201 remarkable similarities in feeding strategy and prey selection. Both taxa are primarily suction

202 feeders, with a large part of their diet coming from squid and small fish, with the addition of benthic
203 invertebrates for the *Delphinapterus* [25-27]. This is reflected in their shared cranial morphology,
204 with a broader and shorter rostrum compared to other taxa [28, 29]. To locate and capture their
205 prey, they both rely heavily on echolocation. These taxa employ similar broadband (BB) hearing
206 frequencies, spanning from ~10 to 120 kHz, with peak sensitivity at mid-range between 40 and 80
207 kHz [25, 26]. This results in comparable levels of skull asymmetry observed in the adults [2] and
208 during the postnatal stages of development, as well as in overlapping inner ear morphologies [30].
209 They also share similar body size of about 5 m in the adults [25, 26], which has been found to
210 correlate with echolocation frequency [31] and prey size [29]. It has been hypothesized that the
211 hearing frequency used by *Delphinapterus* and the other extant genus of Monodontidae (*Monodon*,
212 narwhal) are a key adaptation for navigating their complex polar environment, avoiding ice and
213 finding prey in murky waters [30, 32, 33]. *Globicephala*, unlike other members of Delphinidae, tends
214 to forage at night during deep dives of over 100 meters below the surface, a strategy shared with
215 other toothed whales such as Physeteriidae (sperm whales) [25, 34]. It is possible that the same
216 frequencies used by Monodontidae help *Globicephala* avoid obstacles and find prey in the dark.
217 Another aspect of ecological convergence is the sociality of these two taxa. They both live in large
218 groups spanning from 20 to a few hundred individuals, mostly composed of females and related
219 juveniles, with males living separately and only occasionally joining the larger pods [25, 26]. Due to
220 this behaviour, they retain whistles and other tonal sounds, acoustic features commonly found in
221 species of toothed whales that form complex social groups [35].

222
223 This impressive convergence in ecology and morphological traits in *Delphinapterus* and
224 *Globicephala* is achieved through parallel but different ontogenetic shifts, which are able to
225 overwrite phylogenetic patterns, as has been shown in birds [36] and crocodiles [21, 23]. A major
226 peramorphic shift in skull asymmetry and shape development in prenatal ontogeny of
227 *Delphinapterus* allowed this taxon to evolve its relatively large and asymmetric skull, while an overall
228 deceleration in rate of skull growth in *Globicephala* likely played an important role in the evolution of
229 its distinct morphology among Delphinidae. The anatomical requirements connected to the use of
230 specific echolocating frequencies are likely the main driver behind this phenomenon. Their distant
231 ancestry is still recognizable in the levels of asymmetry in the early fetal stages and in its pattern of
232 change through ontogeny, as well as in the phenotypic trajectory of *Delphinapterus*.

233 234 **(b) Retention of skull symmetry in ontogeny of Phocoenidae**

235 Among Odontoceti, Phocoenidae are commonly described as having immature traits, with a
236 proportionally shorter rostrum and larger braincase compared to delphinids with a similar feeding
237 mode, such as *Lagenorhynchus* [37, 38], and lower levels of asymmetry [2, 13]. *Phocoena* is the
238 only taxon in the dataset to maintain low levels of asymmetry throughout its ontogeny, with early
239 fetuses and adults sharing mostly symmetric skulls (figure 1), a characteristic also reflected in their
240 soft tissue morphology [37]. The closely related *Delphinapterus* starts from similarly low levels of
241 asymmetry but goes on to develop a highly asymmetric skull in adults. Despite drastically different
242 levels of asymmetry and phylogenetic distance, *Phocoena* displays a similar cranial morphology to
243 oceanic dolphins like *Stenella* and *Lagenorhynchus* throughout development (electronic
244 supplementary material, supplemental results, figure S7a-b, table S6). *Phocoena* and
245 *Delphinapterus* also share a similar shortened postnatal development of skull shape (figure 2), as
246 well as a generally paedomorphic trend in allometry inherited from their ancestor (figure 3).
247 Overlapping feeding modes and prey type might be driving the apparent morphological similarities
248 in overall skull shape and growth trajectory between *Phocoena* and some longirostrine oceanic
249 dolphins, but these shared ecological traits do not explain the retention of low levels of skull
250 asymmetry in adults and of other unique characteristics of their development. The unique
251 echolocating abilities of Phocoenidae are the most likely limiting factor in the evolution of this group,
252 and they influence multiple aspects of their ontogeny.

253
254 The majority of the 75 extant species of odontocetes utilize broadband (BB) clicks in the 20-150 kHz
255 for locating prey and communicating, and they present typically high levels of cranial asymmetry, as
256 is the case in the oceanic dolphins present in this dataset and *Delphinapterus*. But Phocoenidae

257 and three other distinct groups, the pygmy and dwarf sperm whales (*Kogia* spp.), the franciscana
258 river dolphin (*Pontoporia blainvillei*), the Lissodelphininae (*Cephalorhynchus* spp., *Lissodelphis*
259 spp.), have convergently evolved the use of narrow-band high-frequency sounds (NBHF) [4]. These
260 taxa have higher sensitivity at the upper end of the hearing spectrum (125-140 kHz) and selectively
261 use these frequencies to communicate rather than lower ones like BB species [4, 13]. It has been
262 hypothesized that ecological pressures have driven the convergent evolution of NBHF. They
263 prevalently inhabit coastal and riverine environments, with the exception of Kogiidae [4]. Using
264 NBHF sounds might be advantageous for navigating the complex environment that surrounds them
265 [39], and it also allows these taxa to avoid predation by large predators such as killer whales, which
266 do not hear sounds at such high frequencies [4, 39]. Nevertheless, they employ a variety of feeding
267 strategies, from the specialized suction feeder *Kogia* to the raptorial feeder *Pontoporia* [4, 39, 40].
268 Morphologically, while they convergently evolved similar inner ear shapes in order to use this
269 specialized type of echolocation [4], they do not consistently display similar skull traits. NBHF taxa
270 tend to retain a largely symmetric skull, similar to that observed in early developmental stages of
271 modern odontocetes [37], as well as in stem taxa [3]. However, this is far from a consistent pattern,
272 with some taxa presenting high levels of asymmetry both in the neurocranium and correlated soft
273 tissues [13, 41]. They also have different rostral morphologies, as this characteristic is tightly linked
274 with feeding strategy in odontocetes [7, 28, 29]. The only trait that they all share is a relatively small
275 body and skull size [4], which has been directly linked to the ability to hearing these high frequency
276 sounds due to scaling of the melon [31].

277
278 As *Phocoena* is the only NBHF taxon in the dataset, its unique ontogeny might be associated with
279 the evolution of this specialized hearing frequency. A shortened and slower postnatal shape growth
280 are the key developmental features that allow adult Phocoenidae to use NBHF sounds, allowing for
281 the correct scaling of the melon relative to its body size [31]. Retention of skull symmetry is likely a
282 product of these other aspects of ontogeny, rather than necessary to develop the ability to use
283 NBHF. This would also explain the asymmetric skull observed in some species of Lissodelphininae
284 [42] and Kogiidae, one of the groups of Odontoceti with the highest skull asymmetry [2, 13], as well
285 as the asymmetric soft tissue morphology of *Pontoporia* [37, 41]. Immature features of Phocoenidae
286 have been attributed to paedomorphic shifts in development occurring in the evolution of this group
287 [37, 38]. Based on the reconstructed allometric trajectories and the development of skull asymmetry
288 in closely related *Delphinapterus*, it is likely that they have instead inherited both skull symmetry and
289 slower and shorter development from the ancestor of the group, rather than secondarily acquiring
290 them through paedomorphic changes in connection to NBHF specifically. However, heterochrony
291 might play a role in the evolution of NBHF hearing in other taxa such as Kogiidae and their
292 ontogeny should be studied in detail to test this hypothesis.

293 294 **(c) Multiple ontogenetic routes to asymmetry**

295 Given the clear divergences observed in the ontogeny of skull shape and asymmetry observed
296 here, data from fossil taxa may elucidate when and why these shifts occurred in the evolution of
297 toothed whales. Cranial asymmetry appears in the earliest toothed whales Xenorophidae† in the
298 mid Oligocene (~30 Mya), likely in connection with the evolution of echolocation [2, 3].
299 Xenorophids† presented a variety of ecological adaptations, from raptorial feeding to specialized
300 suction feeding, reflected in their disparate skull morphologies with varying degrees of telescoping
301 of the neurocranium [43]. As asymmetry levels and degree of telescoping tend to increase gradually
302 during ontogeny in the modern taxa we examined, we can hypothesize that these stem odontocetes
303 had a generally slower or shorter growth compared to extant odontocetes. A medium degree of
304 cranial asymmetry is retained in most odontocetes after this initial shift, with notable increases in
305 Platanistidae, which include the modern South Asian river dolphin (*Platanista gangetica*), and in
306 extant and extinct sperm whales (Physeteriidae and Kogiidae) [2, 43]. These occurrences of higher
307 asymmetry may signal the evolution of convergent ecological adaptations [2, 4, 13, 41] though
308 achieved through different developmental routes, as it is the case in *Delphinapterus* and
309 *Globicephala* in the present dataset. Qualitative studies of the ontogeny of Physeteriidae suggest
310 that they present high levels of asymmetry from the early ontogenetic stages [44], providing
311 additional support for the hypothesis that phylogeny influences the starting level and patterning of

312 asymmetry in ontogeny. If these similar levels of asymmetry were also present in the early fetal
313 stages of closely related Kogiidae, this would explain why they present a highly asymmetrical skull
314 while using NBHF sounds. On the other side of the spectrum, the fossil hyper-longirostrine group
315 Eurhinodelphinidae† presents an overall symmetric skull [2, 45]. This apparent reduction of skull
316 asymmetry might have been coupled with the retention of asymmetrical nasal soft tissues and
317 melon as observed in Pontoporiidae, as this taxon also presents an elongated rostrum [41].
318

319 Another shift occurs at the base of Delphinoidea (Phocoenidae + Monodontidae + Delphinidae) in
320 Kentriodontidae†, a likely paraphyletic fossil group of toothed whales from the early Miocene (~20
321 Mya) [2, 46]. These taxa have overall symmetrical crania, and the type species *Kentriodon pernix*†
322 was reconstructed as having used NBHF sounds based on the morphology of its inner ear [2, 4, 37].
323 It is possible that Phocoenidae and Monodontidae retained their low levels of asymmetry in the
324 early fetal stages from a common ancestor closely related to this extinct group. In fact,
325 *Odobenocetops*†, a fossil taxon with limited echolocating abilities and a mostly symmetric skull, is
326 hypothesized to be a close relative of modern Monodontidae [2]. Therefore, the most parsimonious
327 hypothesis, supported also by our results, is that Monodontidae independently acquired highly
328 asymmetric skulls adapted to BB frequency hearing from an ancestor with a relatively symmetrical
329 cranium and that employed NBHF sounds [2]. This was possible via a shift in rate of asymmetry and
330 overall skull ontogeny in the prenatal stages. *Phocoena* instead retained the ancestral ecology and
331 NBHF hearing frequencies, with the associated pattern of asymmetry and cranial development.
332

333 Fossil and early diverging Delphinidae share moderately high levels of skull asymmetry, most
334 prominent at the dorsal end of the premaxilla, as exemplified by *Eodelphis*† and *Orcinus* (killer
335 whale) [2, 47], similar to what is observed in *Stenella*. Both *Lagenorhynchus* and *Stenella* retain a
336 level of asymmetry likely comparable to their ancestor, which only increases slightly during
337 ontogeny. A shift towards higher asymmetry occurred in the ancestor of the subfamily
338 Globicephalinae, to which *Globicephala* belongs, along with other highly asymmetric taxa such as
339 *Pseudorca* (false killer whale) [2, 7]. It is possible that other genera in this subfamily also have
340 comparatively paedomorphic allometric growth relative to other Delphinidae, while achieving higher
341 levels of skull asymmetry via a longer phenotypic trajectory.
342

343 4. Conclusions

344
345 This first quantitative analysis of cranial shape development in toothed whales demonstrates that a
346 strong phylogenetic signal in early ontogeny is overwritten by ecologically-driven transformations
347 occurring at different stages of growth. A peramorphic shift in prenatal ontogeny of asymmetry of
348 *Delphinapterus* has allowed this taxon to obtain highly asymmetric skulls, similar to that of the
349 delphinid *Globicephala*, while maintaining a paedomorphic growth trend for skull shape.
350 *Globicephala* instead has secondarily slowed its cranial development while maintaining high levels
351 of asymmetry. Ecological factors such as feeding and sociality in the two distantly related taxa have
352 probably driven this convergence, shaping their echolocating abilities and body size [30, 31].
353 *Phocoena* has uniquely low skull asymmetry and truncated postnatal ontogeny compared to the
354 other sampled species. Based on observations of modern and fossil taxa, this pattern is likely
355 retained from the ancestral state of the clade, with additional paedomorphism in postnatal ontogeny
356 being responsible for the juvenile traits and small body size observed in the adults [48]. This
357 paedomorphic tendency is likely correlated with the evolution of NBHF hearing through scaling of
358 the skull and melon in Phocoenidae and other taxa that use these frequencies for echolocation [31].
359 Retention of skull symmetry is a by-product of this lower developmental rate and reflect the
360 ancestral state of Phocoenidae, as it is not consistently present across taxa that employ NBHF
361 sounds [4, 37]. *Stenella* and *Lagenorhynchus* instead show convergent peramorphic patterns of
362 allometry and similar level of skull asymmetry, possibly inherited from the ancestor of Delphinidae
363 [2].

364 Even in a dataset composed of relatively closely related taxa, developmental patterns display large
365 variations. These changes can increment or negate each other through complex interactions in

366 different aspects of development [20]. Studying them is key to better understanding of adaptive
367 patterns of evolution and distinguishing between traits that are directly related with functions and
368 behaviours and those that are a remnant of the phylogenetic history of the clade [16]. Investigating
369 ontogenetic changes in Cetacea has already contributed to reformulate hypotheses on the
370 evolutionary origin of some of their most distinctive traits such as hind limb loss [e.g. 16, 49], teeth
371 simplification and transition to baleen [e.g. 17, 50], ear bone morphology [51], and, here, skull
372 asymmetry. The role of ontogeny in the evolution of unique morphological traits and ecological
373 adaptations remains largely unexplored in many lineages, and we hope that similar approaches to
374 one used here can be applied to future studies in the revived field of evo-devo.
375

376 **5. Materials and Methods**

377 **(a) Morphometric data**

379 The dataset is composed of 58 specimens representing all phases of growth of five odontocete
380 genera from three families: *Delphinapterus* (beluga – Monodontidae), *Phocoena* (common
381 porpoises – Phocoenidae), *Globicephala* (pilot whales – Delphinidae), *Lagenorhynchus* (white-
382 beaked dolphin, white-sided dolphins – Delphinidae), *Stenella* (spinner dolphins, spotted dolphins –
383 Delphinidae). While some of these genera are comprised of multiple species, their morphological
384 similarity and the large phylogenetic distance between genera allows us to use these genera as
385 taxonomic units in the analysis [24] (electronic supplementary material, supplemental methods,
386 dataset S1).

387 Skull morphology was digitized using computed tomography (CT) scanning for fluid preserved
388 specimens and disarticulated osteological specimens (electronic supplementary material,
389 supplemental methods, dataset S2) and using a hand-held surface scanner (Creaform GoSCAN!)
390 for whole osteological specimens. 3D rendering of CT data was performed in Avizo Lite. All meshes
391 were imported in Geomagic Wrap 2017 for cleaning, reduced to 1.5 million faces, and then exported
392 as PLY for landmarking and visualization (electronic supplementary material, supplemental
393 methods).

394 To quantify the shape of the skull, 64 single points landmarks and 43 curves were placed on the
395 surfaces using Stratovan Checkpoint. All points and curves were digitized manually for the right and
396 left side of the cranium to capture asymmetry (electronic supplementary material, supplemental
397 methods, figure S8, table S7). The coordinates for each specimen were exported in PTS format to
398 be analysed.
399

400 **(b) Data analysis**

401 The shape coordinates for all specimens were imported in R [52] for data analysis. After resampling
402 and sliding the curve semilandmark and fixing missing and absent points (electronic supplementary
403 material, supplemental methods), the final dataset used for analysis is composed of 462 points, of
404 which 64 are fixed landmarks and 398 are semilandmarks. Procrustes superimposition (GPA) was
405 performed using the 'gpagen' function in 'geomorph' v. 4.0.1 [53] to align and scale all specimens
406 and extract Centroid Size (CS) to be used as a measure of skull size in allometry analysis. Taxonomic
407 and age information were separately imported to use as covariates. The specimens were binned
408 into four growth categories based on their approximate age and total length: early fetus (from
409 conception to <50% gestation), late fetus and neonate (from >50% gestation to birth, up to the first
410 year of life), juvenile (after the first year until sexual maturity), adult (after sexual maturity) (electronic
411 supplementary material, supplemental methods). Creating these broad age bins allowed to account
412 for possible errors in age and length estimation and created an equal distribution of the dataset
413 between taxa and growth categories, with at least two specimens per stage for each taxon
414 (electronic supplementary material, dataset S1).
415
416
417
418

419 **(i) Asymmetry analysis**

420 Asymmetry levels were assessed only using fixed points landmarks, as using semilandmarks is not
421 implemented consistently in the available methods [2]. We used the function 'bilat.symmetry' from
422 the 'geomorph' package to extract the Directional Asymmetric (DA) shape component and
423 symmetric component of skull shape for each specimen. We then calculated the Euclidean distance
424 between each of the symmetric shape landmarks and the DA shape landmarks was calculated with
425 the 'linear.dist' function in the package 'landVR' v. 0.4 [54]. We used these data to calculate mean
426 distances for each landmark averaging specimens of the same taxon binned in the same growth
427 stage, revealing information on where asymmetry is most visible in the skull. To compare the overall
428 level of asymmetry in the skull across categories and taxa and identify significant differences, we
429 used the 't.test' and 'pairwise.t.test' functions from the 'stats' package v. 4.1.1 [52]. This also
430 produced the mean distance for all the landmarks for each stage and taxon, which is useful to
431 visualize how asymmetry varies in the dataset. As the interparietal bone is variably present in adult
432 odontocetes [18, 55], we decided to remove the three landmarks marked on this bone from the
433 asymmetry analysis presented in the main text (figure 1). However, we did perform the same full set
434 of analyses on the whole skull configuration, and they produced comparable results (electronic
435 supplementary material, supplemental methods, figure S9-S10-S11, table S8).

436 (ii) Shape variation

437 We assessed the variation of shape in the dataset using the whole configuration including
438 semilandmarks by performing a PCA with the 'gm.prcomp' function (electronic supplementary
439 material, supplemental methods) and a phenotypic trajectory analysis across the ontogeny of each
440 taxon with 'trajectory.analysis' [19], both implemented in 'geomorph'. The analysis of trajectory of
441 shape change through ontogeny for each genus was performed on the raw shape coordinates. The
442 function used also allows to significantly test pairwise differences between trajectories.

443 (iii) Allometry analysis

444 As it has been proposed in other mammals [22], we first tested if the prenatal and postnatal
445 allometries were significantly different from each other using the package 'mcp' v. 0.3.0 [56]
446 following [23]. This package calculates the position of a breakpoint in a regression slope and allows
447 us to test if the model with changing slopes is better at explaining the variation than a common
448 slope model. We found that tested models with one break point were consistently preferred
449 (electronic supplementary material, supplemental methods, figure S12a-b, table S4). Given the data
450 binning chosen for the ontogenetic stages, we proceeded to create and test differences of allometry
451 between taxa in the prenatal (early fetus and late fetus/neonate categories) and postnatal (juvenile
452 and adult categories) ontogeny. We used 'procD.lm' in 'geomorph' with specimens divided by genus
453 and stage of growth (prenatal and postnatal) to reconstruct the allometric regressions, and we
454 tested pairwise differences between slopes using 'pairwise' in the package 'RRPP' v. 1.1.2 [57]. We
455 then extracted the regression parameters (slopes and intercepts) and used them to reconstruct
456 ancestral allometric trends, a key step to assess the heterochronic processes at play [20], adapting
457 the methodology presented in [21]. Using a simplified phylogeny with branch lengths extracted from
458 [24], we calculated ancestral slope and intercepts parameters for the nodes using the 'fastAnc'
459 function in 'phytools' v. 1.0 [58]. To assess significant changes in the allometric slopes between
460 ancestral nodes and extant taxa, we used the package 'emmeans' v. 1.7.2 [59] (electronic
461 supplementary material, supplemental methods). Graphics of plots were improved using the
462 'ggplot2' package v. 3.3.5 [60].

463
464 **Data accessibility.** The surface files will be uploaded to the open access repository Phenome10K
465 (<https://www.phenome10k.org/>) after publication. Landmarks, classifiers, and other data necessary
466 for analyses, as well as all the code used, are uploaded to GitHub
467 <https://github.com/AgneseLan/ontogeny-asymmetry-dolphin>
468 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6553285>).

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484

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642 **Figure captions**

643

644 **Figure 1.** Ontogeny of cranial asymmetry in toothed whales. Degree of asymmetry is quantified as
645 the mean distance between the directional asymmetric (DA) and symmetric shape across all
646 landmarks for all specimens of the same genus at each growth stage. The phylogeny drawn on the
647 left highlights the close correspondence between phylogenetic structure and starting level of
648 asymmetry in ontogeny. The skulls on the right represent variation in asymmetry in adult skulls.
649 Landmarks in darker colours indicate more asymmetric regions, as they have a larger distance
650 between the DA and symmetric shape relative to mean of all adults. Significant shifts in asymmetry
651 levels between growth stages in the entire dataset and per genus are indicated by asterisks ('***'
652 $p < 0.001$, '**' $p < 0.01$, '*' $p < 0.05$). Error bars connect the minimum and maximum value of DA-
653 symmetric shape distance for each genus at each stage. See electronic supplementary material,
654 table S1, figure S1-S2 for full results.

655

656 **Figure 2.** Trajectory of skull shape growth (PTA) in each taxon. Direction of ontogeny follows PC1
657 axis, from negative (early fetal stages) to positive values (adults). *Delphinapterus* and *Globicephala*
658 display longer trajectories than the other taxa. See electronic supplementary material, table S2,
659 figure S3 for full results.

660

661 **Figure 3.** Allometric patterns in prenatal and postnatal ontogeny of toothed whales' taxa and their
662 direct ancestors. (a) Regressions of skull shape and size (logCS); (b) Phylogeny with inferred
663 direction of heterochronic change for each node. Similar lower slopes in *Delphinapterus* and
664 *Globicephala* were acquired independently, due to a major pedomorphic shift in *Globicephala* from
665 its peramorphic ancestor. *Phocoena* prenatal slope overlaps the ancestor of Delphinoidea (node 1),
666 while postnatally a pedomorphic shift has occurred. Degree of asymmetry at each node is also
667 reported on the phylogeny. Regressions are represented separately for the prenatal and postnatal
668 stages in electronic supplementary material, figure S5a-b to better visualize difference between taxa
669 and reconstructed ancestral nodes. For significance patterns see electronic supplementary material,
670 figures S4a-b–S6a-b.

